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ABSTRACTS

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Advancing Infectious Disease Classification through Optimized Deep Learning Models: Towards SaMD Integration for Tuberculosis, Pneumonia, COVID, and Healthy State Detection

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Abstract: In the era of SaMD, this research explores the pivotal role of Software as a Medical Device (SaMD) in optimizing deep learning models for the accurate classification of infectious diseases. With a specific emphasis on medical imaging, this study addresses the urgent need for efficient disease prediction methods in the context of general infectious diseases. Medical imaging, particularly through X-ray analysis, has emerged as a vital tool in the early prediction and control of infectious diseases, underscoring the importance of integrating SaMD solutions in infectious disease management. Although different prediction designs have been developed in the past, they face challenges in image segmentation and classification. Thus, a novel hybrid Spider Monkey-based Radial Basis Neural (SMbRBN) framework was designed in this article. This developed model was validated with the X-ray images dataset. The input dataset contains four classes namely Tuberculosis, Pneumonia (Viral), COVID-19 and healthy. Here, the pre-processing mechanism in the designed model filters the unwanted noise features. Moreover, the feature extraction module extracts the features useful for disease prediction and classification. The disease severity probability was analysed for the detected infectious diseases. Furthermore, the effectiveness of the presented work is checked by comparing the estimated outcomes with the existing disease prediction models. The accuracy rate, precision, recall, and f-measure obtained by the proposed method are about 98.78%, 98.33%, 98.33% and 98.22%, respectively. The prediction results and comparative assessment show that the developed model accurately predicts infectious diseases.

Keywords: COVID-19 prediction, Spider Monkey Optimization, Radial Basis Neural System, X-ray Images

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